

SONGS AS A MEANS TO CONVEY EDUCATION MESSAGES FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD STUDENTS

Evie Destiana ¹

^{1,2} PG PAUD Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo

Email: eviedestiana@umsida.ac.id

Received: Feb 07, 2024; Accepted: Feb 08, 2024; Published: Feb 15, 2024;

Abstract: Songs are an integral part of learning activities in early childhood. Every part of learning in early childhood often uses songs as reinforcement in conveying messages in learning. The purpose of this study is to find out how the implementation of songs as a means of conveying educational messages for early childhood students. The research method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection techniques through observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of this study contain a description of the implementation of songs as a means of conveying educational messages for early childhood students. The conclusion of this study is, songs are the right means of conveying educational messages for early childhood students, because through songs educational messages will be more easily understood and remembered by children at any time..

Keywords: Songs, Education Messages, Early Childhood

Introduction

The early childhood curriculum establishes indicators of art as educational tools that are beneficial to the development of students. In the field of music, its application can be done through playing musical instruments and singing. Art education is one of the educational media to improve children's positive personality [1]. Ideally, art education should begin to be implemented and taught from a young age, since then a person's personality begins to form [2].

Art education provided in schools is not only to develop the child's personality but also to help the occurrence of multiple intelligences in children [3]. Merritt's research in the book 'Symphony Brain' [4] concerning the correlation between music and intelligence explains that music is beneficial in stimulating children's IQ, EQ and SQ. Furthermore, according to him, music that is useful for stimulating interest in IQ, EQ and SQ will be more appropriate to be played from an early age, around 0 to 8 years. At that time, talents that were useful for the future of children began to form, so it was appropriate for early childhood to be introduced to music.

Music can be used to stimulate children in carrying out activities related to gross and fine motor movements. In general, the implications of learning music in public schools, especially at the early childhood level, can be seen after it is integrated with other fields or subjects that are appropriate to the learning themes taught by the teacher during the learning process. Song lyrics used in learning are associated with learning objectives or themes. While the melodies are widely used, the melodies of popular songs are unlimited.

Creativity that is done more related to the lyrics or the text of the poem. In general, the teacher does not compose songs, but the lyrics that are combined with the melody of the

song have a creative side of their own. For example, when the information you want to convey is related to the environment, then there is a tendency for a song with a cheerful rhythm. Some songs are related to the theme of divinity, so they tend to play rhythmically. The selected note intervals in the song melody are not too far away, and are easy for children to sing. The duration of the song is also identical or in accordance with the characteristics of the child, which is not too long. Most teachers don't pay much attention to the appropriate ambitus of the child, so the child can just sing as they like, and as they please. This actually has fun for children, more natural and more expressive.

The teacher's goal of using songs in learning is more meant by the context of the learning approach in early childhood and also the context of learning achievement goals. The approach in question is playing while learning, and this is very appropriate to do with communication using song media. Related to the learning objectives, that with the lyrics sung, apart from being more fun, it is also easier for children to accept.

The lyrics are usually not only adapted to the theme, but also adjusted by looking at the child's basic competencies, the indicators of which are based on the child's age. Based on the theme, the lyrics are related to my environment, myself, my needs, social religion, my family, animals, and my country.

Children will remember the songs taught by the teacher, and this can be a guide or knowledge for children related to the message of the songs sung by children. In his article, Wadiyo stated that the scope of development given by music is the scope of religious development, especially at the level of developing religious values and morals which is done by singing songs that contain religion. Another scope of development is that it contains a combination of music and dance, especially to develop gross and fine motor skills, and is added to the main musical material, namely singing to develop potential language skills [5].

Methodology

This research is a qualitative research with observation method. Sugiyono stated that observation in a narrow sense is a research process observing situations and conditions. According to Suharsimi Arikunto Observation is direct observation of an object that is in the on going environment covering various activities of attention to the study of objects using sensing. Based on some understanding of the observations of these experts, we can now draw conclusions. In general, observation is an activity to find out something from phenomena. These activities are based on knowledge and ideas that aim to obtain information from the phenomenon under study. This research was carried out in the Sidoarjo Regency area.

Results and Discussion

The following are the results and discussion to answer research questions in this study regarding how to implement music learning in the context of integrated learning at the early childhood level, which is carried out by teachers. According to [6], the early childhood curriculum which shows indicators of art emphasizes how art can be used as an educational tool that is beneficial to student development. It is not used to force students to be able to make art. In its application during the learning process, music can be taught through singing and playing musical instruments, but the main focus in learning is not on the music itself, but rather on the educational messages conveyed through music or songs.

The teaching materials developed are contained in the Protah or Early Childhood Annual Program. The art is taught by interpreting Protah which is divided into Scope of Development, Level of Achievement of Development, Indicators, Themes, and Week Time Allocation. The scope of development is composed of religious and moral values, which consist of physical gross motor, fine motor, and physical health. In addition, within the

scope of development there are cognitive aspects consisting of general knowledge and science, the concepts of shape, color, size and pattern. Within the scope of this development are also the concepts of numbers, symbols, and letters. There is also scope related to language development.

Other aspects besides those previously mentioned are all scopes in social development. According to [11], art education should ideally be instilled from childhood because it is during this period that a person's personality begins to form. What is done and developed in the learning process for children at the preschool level in this context is early childhood, where art is used as a medium of education, has been considered as something appropriate. Art education provided in schools is also intended to help multi-intelligence students [7]. The results of [8] show that music helps children stimulate many intelligences. In connection with this interest, it would be more appropriate if music was listened to at an early age.

In this annual program, the development scope is described at the level of achievement of development and explained to be implemented with written indicators as guidelines that will be developed in the teaching and learning process. Starting from the scope of development which is explained using the basic indicators, all of them use the expected theme and time of the week during learning practices [12]. The theme determined in the annual learning program is about me, my environment, my needs, animals, plants, recreation, my homeland and the universe. Based on the annual program, teachers can choose what and how learning practices should be done. For the field of learning in relation to art, teachers can choose from what is contained in the program, especially from the indicators that must be carried out by the teacher. Indicators included in the annual program that must be carried out by the teacher in the teaching and learning process are for example indicators of head, hand, foot movement while following the rhythm of music or rhythm. This shows that music and dance are lessons that cannot be separated [9]. points out a number of benefits of integration, including applying basic skills in real-life situations, raising standards, increasing teacher creativity, reducing teacher isolation and providing a more positive classroom climate. According to [10], national music standards deal with 'understanding the relationship between music, other arts, and disciplines outside the arts', and 'understanding music in relation to history and culture' embracing the concept of integration of quality for students to develop subject understanding. deeper through their interactions with one another.

Summary

Art teaching materials in Early Childhood refer to themes related to childrens lives and their environment. Music material, as well as being used as an integrative main subject and other material to instill knowledge and examples of behavior as well as aesthetic education tools in relation to the scope of development and the level of achievement of development as outlined in the annual program.

Reference

- [1] Banoe, Pono.(1985). *Kamus Istilah Musik*, Jakarta: CV
- [2] Baru Djohan.(2010). *Respon Emosi Musikal*, Bandung : Lubuk Agung
- [3] Evans, Paul. "Motivation" dalam Gary E. McPherson (ed.).(2016).*The Child as Musician: A Handbook of Musical Development*, Oxford University Press
- [4] Gardner, Howard.(2013).*Multiple Intelligences*, terjemahan Yelvi Andri Zaimur, Jakarta: Daras Books Hallam, Susan. "Musicality" dalam Gary E. McPherson (ed.).(2016). *The Child as Musician: A Handbook of Musical Development*, Oxford University Press
- [5] Hurlock, Elisabeth B.(2014). *Psikologi Perkembangan: Suatu Pendekatan Sepanjang*

Rentang Kehidupan. Erlangga: Jakarta

- [6] Hodges, Donald A. "The Child Musician's Brain" dalam Gary E. McPherson (ed.). (2016). *The Child as Musician: A Handbook of Musical Development*, Oxford University Press
- [7] Koster, Joan Bouza. (2012). *Growing Artists: Teaching the Arts to Young Children*, fifth edition USA: Wadsworth Change Learning
- [8] Latipah, Eva. (2017). *Psikologi Dasar: Bagi Guru*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya
- [9] Leaman, Oliver. (2005). *Estetika Islam: Menafsir Seni dan Keindahan*, terjemahan Irfan Abubakar, Bandung: Mizan
- [10] Mashar, Riana. (2011). *Emosi Anak Usia Dini dan Strategi Pengembangannya*, Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Grup
- [11] Masitoh, Dkk. (2009). *Strategi Pembelajaran TK*, Jakarta : Universitas Terbuka
- [12] Muali, Chusnul. (2019). "Kajian Refleksi Teori Pengembangan Karakter Anak Melalui Pembelajaran Agama Perspektif Albert Bandura", jurnal Pendidikan dan Manajemen Islam *Fikrotuna*, volume 9no.1, Juli 2019, halaman 1031-1052. P-ISSN 2441-2401; e-ISSN 2477-5622.
- [13] Merritt, S. (2003). *Simfoni Otak*. Bandung: Kaifa.
- [14] Tarwiyah, Tuti. (2004). *Analisis Nilai-nilai Pendidikan Dalam Lagu-lagu Daerah Betawi*. Harmonia: Jurnal Pengetahuan dan Pemikiran Seni Harmonia, 6(1).
- [15] Wadiyo. (2015). *Music As An Integrated Education Tools For Preschool Students*. HARMONIA : Journal of Arts Research and Education 15 (2) (2015), 144-151 Available online at <http://journal.unnes.ac.id/nju/index.php/harmonia>
DOI:10.15294/harmonia.v15i2.4691
- [16] Wardani, Cut Kamaril. (2006). *Pendidikan Seni Berbasis Budaya in Meningkatkan Multi Kecerdasan*. Jurnal Kagunan, I(1).